

Geographic Variation Among Child Malnutrition Correlates in Tamil Nadu: A Multilevel Approach

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Abstract— Maternal and child malnutrition in low-income countries is a major public health challenge in India. Socioeconomic status and maternal health factors are associated with child malnutrition, and it remains under-prioritised. The study aims to quantify geographic variation in maternal, child and household risk factors across villages and districts in Tamil Nadu. The National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5, 2019-2022) dataset was used for analysis. 6373 live children were included. Multilevel logistic regression models were applied, and intraclass correlation coefficients were estimated using null models. The results show that the majority of variation in socioeconomic conditions, maternal health indicators and child health practices is concentrated at the village-level, with minimal variation across districts. The key risk factors include poverty, unimproved sanitation, unsafe child stool disposal, insufficient ANC visits, early marriage, diarrhoea, and pneumonia exhibit strong village-level associations. The micro-level inequalities are masked at the district-level. Household conditions, maternal health, and child healthcare practices are shaped at the village-level.

Keywords— Geographic variation, multilevel analysis, village-level, district-level, maternal and child

I. INTRODUCTION

Maternal and child malnutrition in low and middle-income countries involves both undernutrition and the increasing rate of overweight and obesity, posing a serious public health concern [1]. In 2021, nearly 5.6 million children under 5 years died (38 deaths per 1000 live births). In low-income countries, there are 67 deaths of children under 5 years old per 1000 live births. The risk of child mortality was increasing due to lack of access to essential healthcare services and vaccination, inadequate nutrition, unsafe drinking water, and poor sanitation. It includes the preventable communicable and infectious diseases [2]. Inadequate antenatal and postnatal care increases risks to children. Poverty reduction, improved socioeconomic status, and maternal education are strongly linked with child nutrition, yet remain under-prioritised [3] [4]. Poverty is a multidimensional situation in which an individual faces many disadvantages in health, education, and living conditions simultaneously. Economically disadvantaged households often lack the resources needed to ensure adequate nutrition and healthy living conditions, which increases the risk of poor child health outcomes [5], [6]. Adolescent girls from poor households are more likely to experience early marriage, adverse birth outcomes such as low birth weight, risk factors leading to child malnutrition, and anaemia. The increased risk of child marriage on children's nutritional outcomes is more related to poverty, such as low maternal education, poor household economic conditions, and inadequate access to maternal healthcare services [7].

Evidence from previous studies suggests that poor intergenerational health among mothers is more strongly associated with child malnutrition. The prevalence of anthropometric indicators among under-5 children remains high in India. According to the NFHS dataset, stunting, wasting, and underweight in India (2019-2022) are 33.5%, 18.6% & 29.5%, respectively [8]. Previous studies focusing on a single geographic level tend to overestimate the influence of that level. Understanding the geographic distribution of risk factors in India requires a multilevel approach, as influences operate at household, village, district, and state levels. Multilevel studies show that village-level factors, along with district- and state-level conditions, play an important role in shaping household deprivation and inequality [5], [9], [10]. This study identifies key risk factors associated with poor child health outcomes and emphasises the need to identify specific regions where child malnutrition risk factors tend to cluster, enabling interventions to be better targeted. This study aims to quantify geographic variation in maternal, child, and household-level risk factors across villages and districts in Tamil Nadu.

II. METHODS

The National Family Health Survey, round five (NFHS-5, 2019-2022), data are used for the analysis. This data provides comprehensive information on fertility, mortality, maternal and child healthcare, including children's nutritional status, for each state and district of India. The data was collected from 6 36,699 households, 7,24,115 eligible women aged 15-49, and 1,101,839 eligible men aged 15-54[11]. In the state of Tamil Nadu, the information were gathered from 32 districts, 1,304 villages, 27,929 households, 25,650 women, and 3,372 men [12]. 6,373 children alive at the time of the interview were included in this study.

The risk factors of children's malnutrition have been dichotomized according to the previous studies [13], [14]. Wealth index poor, antenatal care visit, complete vaccination, married early (before 18 years), mother's body mass index, poor diet intake, clean cooking fuel, improved sanitation facility, improved water facility, had diarrhea in past two weeks, had pneumonia in past two weeks, unsafe stool disposal of children, taken vitamin A, birth order more than 6 birth, early breastfeeding (within 1 hour), women's educational status, taken oral rehydration solution, unmet needs[5]. Three geographic levels: districts, villages, where households are nested. Each level plays a distinct role in influencing the risk of child malnutrition. Districts manage service delivery, and villages shape daily social and economic conditions. Individual level (children – level 1) was nested within village (level 2) and district (level 3). Multilevel logistic models were applied with individuals nested within villages and districts. For each risk factor, null models were fitted to estimate variance components at the different levels along with Intraclass correlation coefficients (ICCs) [5], [14]. Analysis was performed using software RStudio V.2025.09.2.

III. RESULTS

Nearly 22% of households do not use clean cooking fuel; 24.4% do not have access to improved sanitation facilities; and nearly 5% of households rely on unimproved drinking water sources. 95% rely on improved drinking water sources. Almost 72% of households practice unsafe disposal of child stool, which reflects poor hygiene. 406 women had visited less than 4 antenatal care visits. 12.2% of mothers have a body mass index below 18.5 kg/m². 967 (15.2%) women married before the age of 18 years, and 17.9% reported an unmet need for family planning. Skilled birth attendance was high in Tamil Nadu. 61.8% of children had delayed initiation of breastfeeding, and 22.8% were not fully vaccinated. 60.7% of children have not received vitamin A. However, a poor diet was observed among 30% of children. The prevalence of diarrhoea and pneumonia symptoms was low. Among 237 (3.7%) children who had diarrhoea, only 110 (46.4%) had not received oral rehydration solution (ORS).

Socioeconomic disadvantage, with 17.6% households classified as poor based on the wealth index. Table 1 represents the hierarchical geographic distribution of household, maternal and child health factors in Tamil Nadu.

Table 1: Geographic Distribution of Socio-economic, Household, Maternal, and Child Risk Factors in Tamil Nadu

Domain	Risk Factors	Districts	Villages	Number of eligible children (n)	Number of children at risk n(%)
Household Factors	Not using clean cooking fuel	32	603	6373	1393 (21.9)
	Not having an improved sanitation facility	32	605	6068	1481 (24.4)
	Not having an improved drinking water source	32	136	6068	299 (4.9)
	Unsafe disposal of a child's stool	32	947	3421	2460 (71.9)
Socioeconomic Factors	Households in the poor wealth index	32	515	6373	1120 (17.6)
	Mother illiterate	29	76	6373	105 (1.6)
Maternal Characteristics & Care	Women married before 18 years old	32	549	6373	967 (15.2)
	Fewer than four antenatal care visits	32	270	5099	406 (8.0)
	Mother BMI < 18.5 kg/m ²	32	457	6234	763 (12.2)
	Unmet need for family planning	32	632	6373	1138 (17.9)
	Not a skilled birth attendant	6	11	6373	13 (0.2)
	Birth order six and above	3	3	6373	3 (0.0)
	Not initiated early breastfeeding	32	1090	5187	3203 (61.8)
Children health	Children (6–23 months) not fully vaccinated	32	833	6373	1454 (22.8)
	Poor dietary diversity	32	986	6373	1919 (30.1)
	Improper intake of Vitamin A supplementation	32	1022	3813	2314 (60.7)
	Had diarrhoea in the past two weeks	32	209	6373	237 (3.7)
	Oral Rehydration solution was not given during diarrhoea	31	105	237	110 (46.4)
	Presence of pneumonia symptoms	21	55	6373	63 (1.0)

Table 2: Most of the variability is concentrated at the village-level for household and socioeconomic characteristics, which exhibit substantial geographic variation across Tamil Nadu. Wealth index-poor indicating micro-level economic inequality, which shows high variability at the village-level (ICC = 0.45) compared with the districts (ICC = 0.12). No proper access to drinking water and unimproved sanitation shows clustering at the village-level, highlighting an uneven distribution of water supply, while the district-level variation was negligible (ICC = 0.004). Not using clean cooking fuel and unimproved sanitation facilities also showed meaningful clustering at the village-level (ICC=0.39 and ICC=0.54, respectively). The inadequacy of a poor diet shows limited geographic clustering. Less utilisation of antenatal care (<4 visits) exhibits very high village-level clustering (ICC=0.91), with no district-level variation, which shows a strong influence on healthcare access. Early marriage

(<18 years) demonstrated moderate village-level variation (ICC = 0.379), than district-level effects (ICC = 0.044), which reflects broader regional patterns

Table 2: Multilevel Intra-class correlation of null model for Household, Maternal, and Child Risk Factors

Domain	Risk Factors	ICC (District)	ICC (PSU/Village)
Household Factors	Not using clean cooking fuel	0.18	0.39
	Not having an improved sanitation facility	0.09	0.54
	Not having an improved drinking water source	0.00	0.96
	Unsafe disposal of child's stool	0.02	0.66
Socioeconomic Factors	Households in the poor wealth index	0.12	0.45
	Mother illiterate	0.00	0.95
Maternal Characteristics & Care	Women married before 18 years old	0.04	0.38
	Fewer than four antenatal care visits	0.00	0.91
	Mother BMI < 18.5 kg/m ²	0.00	0.51
	Unmet need for family planning	0.00	0.43
	Not a skilled birth attendant	0.03	0.94
	Birth order six and above	0.00	0.98
Children health	Not initiated early breastfeeding	0.04	0.50
	Children (6–23 months) not fully vaccinated	0.01	0.16
	Poor dietary diversity	0.00	0.11
	Improper intake of Vitamin A supplementation	0.01	0.37
	Had diarrhoea in the past two weeks	0.00	0.80
	Oral Rehydration Solution was not given during diarrhoea	0.00	0.89
	Presence of pneumonia symptoms	0.00	0.95

A maternal body mass index <18.5 kg/m² showed village clustering (ICC = 0.51), which indicates localised vulnerability for the mother's nutritional status. There is an uneven utilisation of reproductive health services, as the unmet need for family planning showed a variation across the villages. High village-level clustering for mother's education attainment, which highlights community-level disparities. Child health outcomes varied with minimal contribution across districts and high variation across villages. Children who had diarrhoea showed a high variation (ICC = 0.79), and pneumonia symptoms showed

very strong variation (ICC = 0.95) at the village-level. This emphasises the local environmental conditions and healthcare access. Unsafe child stool disposal practices, delayed initiation of breastfeeding, and vitamin A intake showed high variation across villages. No intake of oral rehydration solution (ORS) for children with diarrhoea also showed high village-level variation (ICC = 0.89), indicating uneven treatment practices. No skilled birth attendant showed limited district-level variation (ICC = 0.025), highlighting substantial disparities in access to delivery care across communities. Full immunisation coverage demonstrated moderate village-level variation (ICC = 0.16).

IV. DISCUSSION

The study demonstrates that the majority of geographic variation in maternal, child, and household-level risk factors in Tamil Nadu is concentrated at the village-level rather than the district-level, according to *A. Jain, J. Rodger et al.* The consistency of this finding shows that villages account for the largest share of variation in nutrition-related factors. Household and socioeconomic indicators, such as wealth, source of drinking water, and improved sanitation, and maternal health indicators, such as inadequate antenatal care and maternal undernutrition, as well as child health outcomes, such as diarrhoea, pneumonia, and unsafe stool disposal, exhibit strong village clustering, indicating pronounced micro-level variations within districts [15].

According to *R. Kim et al.*, the pronounced strong village clustering of maternal healthcare, low utilisation of provided services, consistently shows that maternal health reflects a life-course that has intergenerational disadvantage by influencing child outcomes. Maternal vulnerabilities reflect early-life disadvantages that cluster child health risk within villages. Child morbidity and care highlight the strong influence of local environments and service access at the village-level. The present study shows substantial inequality within a single state [14].

The study "The burden of child and maternal malnutrition and trends in its indicators in the states of India" reports national evidence of significant state-level differences in malnutrition. This present study indicates that there is high variation across village-levels and minimal variation across district-levels. These patterns reflect malnutrition, poor living conditions, maternal undernutrition, and limited access to health care. It emphasises the need for village-focused interventions to reduce malnutrition and related health risks[16].

According to *P. Paul et al.*'s malnutrition-related risks are mainly clustered at the village-level rather than the district-level, indicating substantial local inequalities. Early marriage (<18 years) is closely linked to these village-level variations. Adolescent married women are more likely to be poor, undernourished, less educated, and to receive inadequate antenatal care. Children born to these women face significantly higher risks of stunting, underweight, and anaemia. These results highlight that there are health service gaps [17].

V. CONCLUSION

The study demonstrates that, despite relatively high coverage of household facilities, maternal and child health services persist at the village-level in Tamil Nadu. Household, socioeconomic, maternal, and child health factors are strongly clustered at the village-level, with minimal variation at the district-level. Wide village-level differences in child health outcomes and care practices underscore the role of the local environment and access to essential services. Overall, the findings suggest that district-level analysis masks the importance of micro-level disparities. Villages that are highly clustered should focus on strategies that address the household living conditions, maternal and child healthcare utilisation, and practices to reduce the risk and improve

health outcomes in Tamil Nadu. These findings underscore the importance of multilevel strategies in addressing the correlates of child malnutrition in Tamil Nadu.

VI. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors acknowledge the Demographic and Health Surveys (DHS) program for providing free access to Fifth National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5) data.

VII. FUNDING

The author(s) received no funding for this work.

VIII. DECLARATION OF COMPETING INTEREST

Conflict of interest none.

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